

Design and synthesis of “AIEE” luminogen, modified itto “AIE”luminogen by small modification and used forlatent fingerprint imaging

Laxmi Raman Adil¹and Parameswar Krishnan Iyer^{1,2}

¹Department of Chemistry and²Center for Nanotechnology, Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati,

Guwahati, Assam 781 039, India

pki@iitg.ernet.in, Mob No. 9954172726

Abstract

Latent fingerprints (LFPs)has various whorls, arches and loops that are identical for a person. As a result almost a century fingerprints used as a means of identification (1). Aggregation inducedemission (AIE) luminogens are highly fluorescent in nanoparticle form and solid statebut less or not fluorescentin the soluble state. Classical luminogensshow opposite properties then AIE molecules, these molecules are calledaggregation causedquenching (ACQ)molecules. There are some luminogens they show higher emission in semi aggregated state they are called aggregation induced enhance emission(AIEE) luminogens (2).So keeping benefits of AIE molecule we synthesizedTPBZ and TPBC.We used it for latent fingerprintimaging on different substrates. TPBZ and TPBC characterized by MALDI-TOF, ¹HNMR,¹³C NMR and nanoparticles studied by DLS spectroscopy.

Keywords: AIE, AIEE, Latent fingerprint imaging.

Fig. Pictorial representation of visualization of LFPs by TPBC

References

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